

Data Management Plan (DMP)

A Supervised Machine Learning Approach for Assessing Grant Peer Review Reports

1 Data collection and documentation

1.1 Type of data

This study combines qualitative human annotation and transformer-based machine-learning approaches to assess characteristics of grant proposal peer review reports submitted to the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF).

The primary data used in this study is a corpus of SNSF grant peer review reports, written in English by external reviewers, of all proposals that have been submitted to the SNSF in the funding scheme Project Funding from all calls with submission end dates between October 2016 and April 2024. The dataset consists of 47'522 review reports for 13'653 proposals. The data is stored in a CSV format with a volume of ca. 350 MB. The data includes metadata about each proposal, such as the funding call and demographics of the applicants, metadata about each review, such as demographics about the reviewer, and the texts of the reviews themselves along with a numerical assessment of the reviewed proposal. The full list of data variables will be described in a report and made available alongside academic publications. The data corpus is anonymised with respect to proposal and review IDs as well as the peer review texts which do not contain any names of applicants, co-applicants or project partners. Follow-up studies may potentially use the primary data from this study extended with later calls and additional funding schemes (e.g. Sinergia).

The study has produced the following data:

1. a collection of code scripts to process the raw data. The code scripts clean and format the raw data to be used for the manual annotation of sentences as well as the training data used in the machine learning analyses. This includes the segmentation of the grant peer review texts into sentences, cleaning the texts by removing special characters and HTML/CSS formatting, creating a unique identifier for each sentence, and sampling sentences for the annotation. The code scripts are written in R.
2. a detailed annotation codebook capturing 12 categories that reflect characteristics of grant peer review reports at the sentence level based on SNSF evaluation guidelines and principles.
3. a set of 3'000 manually annotated sentences, which were sampled from the primary data. The annotation was done in several rounds by four trained annotators, who followed the instructions from the annotation codebook. The data is stored in a CSV format with a volume of ca. 1.5 MB.

4. a collection of code scripts for fine-tuning the machine-learning models. The code scripts contain pre-processing of the data from the annotated sample to fit the input structure of the machine learning models. This includes reshaping and splitting the data into training and testing sets. The code scripts contain the procedures for fine-tuning pre-trained transformer models for the text classification task using the annotated sample. This data may be relevant for external researchers interested in performing future replications and extensions. The code scripts are written in Python.
5. the fine-tuned models that can be loaded and used for prediction purposes to classify text into the 12 categories of grant peer review characteristics. The models are saved in a safetensors format with a volume of ca. 400 MB each.

1.2 Data collection

This study relies on grant proposal peer review reports submitted by external experts to the SNSF as part of the scientific evaluation procedure of the SNSF. This data is stored by the SNSF in an SNSF internal database.

The SNSF provided the data to the research team at University College Dublin, who is conducting the study in collaboration with the SNSF in an anonymized form for the study. This means that the identifiers of the proposals and reviews as well as the names of all applicants, co-applicants and project partners were replaced in the texts by placeholders. The SNSF extracted the data relevant for the project via SQL queries, pre-processed and anonymised the data in R as described above and delivered it to the collaborators in Dublin via CSV files stored in a Microsoft SharePoint folder hosted by the SNSF with restricted access. All researchers (including annotators) involved in the study signed confidentiality agreements to work with this data. The annotators who produced the manually annotated sentences as described in section 1.1 (point 3), did not have full access to the data and only received the data relevant for annotation, comprising randomly sampled and anonymized review sentences without any identifying information.

1.3 Documentation and Metadata

The project team provides metadata of the raw dataset for use within the project, but due to data privacy laws no raw data from this project can be shared. Documentation of the data processing and classification steps is produced and is explained in forthcoming scientific publications. We transparently document thorough testing and validation of the algorithm.

The code for fine-tuning the classification models and the models themselves resulting from this work is published, along with detailed documentation of the textual input and classification output of the models.

The detailed annotation codebook that is developed during the project is shared in full.

All further material and documentation that will serve for replication purposes will be deposited on a data repository.

2 Ethics, legal and security issues

2.1 Addressing ethical issues

The primary data used in this study is confidential, protected by data protection laws (in particular, FADP). To safeguard against misuse of the data and ensure that the privacy of the grant applicants and peer reviewers is adequately protected, the project team made the data de-facto anonymous and took procedural measures to regulate data access. De-facto anonymization was achieved in the following ways:

- No data about the names of the grant applicants or peer reviewers or identifying information about the grant proposals or reviews were provided.
- The names of grant applicants, co-applicants and project partners were removed from the texts of the peer reviews before data delivery.

2.2 Data Access and Security

The main issue of data privacy relating to the implementation of the project has been addressed with the anonymization process. Data security was addressed by limiting access to the project data to the members of the project team. Data and code scripts were treated with strict confidentiality and stored in two private locations. The dataset is located in a private and password-protected SNSF Microsoft SharePoint folder. Code scripts and output files (tables and plots with aggregated results) were shared in a private GitHub repository with access granted exclusively to the project team. No input data was shared on GitHub. In addition, as mentioned above, all project collaborators have signed a confidentiality agreement with the SNSF. The training of the machine-learning models was performed locally without access to the internet to prevent any potential data leakage or network interference. There are no anticipated issues or concerns resulting from the sole access to the fine-tuned models. Given the confidential nature of the grant proposal peer review texts and their metadata, neither the primary data of the study nor the annotated sentences can be made publicly accessible.

2.3 Copyright and Intellectual Property Rights

The SNSF is the owner of the data and the deliverables. Aggregated output data and code scripts for model training are made accessible open source via GitHub under MIT license. The fine-tuned models are shared open-source via Hugging Face Hub under MIT license as well.

3 Data storage and preservation

3.1 Data storage and back-up

The primary data for this project belong to SNSF and is stored on internal SNSF servers with daily backups. The data is archived every 6 weeks, every 6 months, and every year automatically through

SNSF IT services. For the purpose of this study, the anonymised primary data and the samples were shared with the project team via a SNSF shared Microsoft SharePoint folder. Access to this folder is password protected and limited to the members of the project team.

The annotation sample was shared with annotators via a dedicated SNSF shared Microsoft SharePoint folder with restricted access.

The code scripts for the machine learning analyses are stored on GitHub (<https://github.com/>) and are made public on Zenodo.

After the completion of the machine learning analyses, the fine-tuned models will be hosted on the Hugging Face Hub (<https://huggingface.co/docs/hub/index>).

3.2 Data preservation plan

All primary data are stored in SNSF internal SQL databases and are preserved without time limit. The annotated data is stored on an internal SNSF SharePoint site. The collected aggregated output data, code scripts for machine-learning analyses and the fine-tuned models are in addition preserved on the Zenodo repository with a DOI.

4 Data sharing and reuse

4.1 Data sharing

The primary data and the sample of 3'000 annotated sentences are confidential and cannot be made publicly accessible due to data protection laws, in particular the Federal Act on Data Protection (FADP). The code scripts in R to process this confidential data can also not be made publicly accessible. The annotation codebook is publicly shared and published on Zenodo. The code scripts in Python for fine-tuning the machine-learning models are published on GitHub, with a copy published on Zenodo for replication purposes. The fine-tuned models will be hosted on the Hugging Face Hub, with a copy on Zenodo to enable an open-source access to the models. The data and models are further described in detail in forthcoming scientific papers, which also include anonymised and aggregated data in form of results.

4.2 Protection limitations

Data access limitations are due to legal, ethical, copyright, and confidentiality issues.

4.3 Digital repositories

Zenodo is used a main data repository for this project. Zenodo complies with the FAIR Data Principles.

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